

Recommended citation: Leppänen, M. M., & Kuula, P. H. (2019). Experiences from collaborative online education for degree and further education on circular economy. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 699-709). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656527.

Experiences from collaborative online education for degree and further education on circular economy

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Conference Key Areas: Open and Online Teaching and Learning, Lifelong Learning

Keywords: online teaching, circular economy, continuous learning, cooperative learning

ABSTRACT

Life-long learning has been recognized to be a powerful route to meet the transient competence needs. The education during employment gives a chance to renew competences and skills.

Circular Economy (CE) is one topical issue pushing us to update our skills and competences. To promote and accelerate the necessary and disruptive change in a culture, we should educate both future and present professionals. To focus on specific perspective in all applications rather than general design, a novel course on circular economy of infrastructures was created in co-operation with industry.

In this paper, experiences from two CE courses are discussed to point out the special questions in lifelong learning especially considering the cooperative learning and student diversity.

The participants with different backgrounds, i.e. the young degree students and further education students, were mixed together in co-operative learning schemes. The adult learners were supposed to provide their practical working experience and holistic approach, and the undergraduates in turn their modern learning and information retrieval skills.

The course has been organized twice, at two universities simultaneously. The course consists of six contact teaching days. The lectures were recorded and available on line through Adobe Connect (AC). The tasks and quizzes were distributed in Moodle. The project work was done in groups composed of various participants. In latter implementation, the flipped learning methods were applied.

Based on the feedback, the participants were very satisfied with the course. However, the low commitment of further education students shown as drop-outs and various delays caused problems especially in group work, thus overloading the degree students.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Education of Circular Economy

Circular Economy (CE) has been one of the key targets of the Finnish government [1]. In the national road map to CE, one important measure is introducing the circular economy perspectives to teaching in all education levels [2]. According to a recent study [3], the education for sustainable development is still not integrated in all engineering education in Finnish universities despite committing to the sustainable development in their strategies. To implement the strategy, a cross-disciplinary module on CE, bringing together engineering and business perspectives, has been established in Tampere University.

Infrastructure construction is a very material and energy intensive sector. The use of recycled materials and the design of the structures are in a key role in promoting CE in infrastructure construction. The environmental legislation and public procurement methods create boundary conditions on the implementation of CE. The inquiries and discussions with the experts, contractors and authorities have also shown that the lack of knowledge is one of the major obstacles for the utilization of recovered and secondary materials in earthworks and infrastructure projects. Therefore, the industry was very interested to support the education of CE for infra engineering students and professionals.

1.2 Co-operative learning

Based on the variety of students and complexity of the subject, the chosen pedagogical approach for CE courses was co-operative learning. Co-operative learning is an effective method in problem-based learning, providing a possibility to practice and learn useful meta skills such as team work, negotiation, argumentation and presentation.

In co-operative learning the learners are working together to accomplish shared learning goals and complete jointly specific tasks and assignments. The groups are typically heterogeneous, especially in terms of achievement motivation and task orientation. The longer a cooperative group works together, the more caring their relationships will tend to be, the greater the social support they will provide for each other, the more committed they will be to each other's success, and the more influence members will have over each other. [4]

1.3 Lifelong learning

Oosi et al. (2019) are stating that "learning is becoming a key asset when we are answering to various social and economic challenges". It has been recognized that to agilely adapt to the future challenges caused by the megatrends, such as, among others, digitalization, urbanization, robotics and climate change, there is a need for re- and further education. Life-long learning, also called continuous learning, could be a solution for reskilling, upgrading skills or developing the skills required by the changing working life. [5]

1.4 Student diversity

When degree students and adult students are combined, the student diversity should be considered. To be able to provide student-centered teaching you need to know who your students are. Students are coming from a range of diverse backgrounds and have differing aspirations, levels of motivation, attitudes towards teaching and learning and responses to learning environment and teaching practices. Especially adult learners are having diverse knowledge, perspectives, bias and life experiences. *Fig. 1* summarizes the main key dimensions of student diversity that may affect learning and teaching. [6]

Fig. 1. Some of the key dimensions of student diversity. (UNSW is referring to UNSW Sydney, i.e. the University of New South Wales, one of Australia's leading research and teaching universities.) [6]

1.5 On-line learning

On-line or distance learning, i.e. learning through an internet connection, has been considered as a solution especially for further education of working adult learners. On-line learning can be either synchronous or asynchronous. Synchronous means “at the same time” and typically the learners meet and work online in a virtual classroom. Especially asynchronous e-learning offers working professionals a flexible alternative to upgrade their knowledge, since the schedule of learning is free.

On the other hand, on-line learning requires higher self-direction and better self and time management skills than traditional class room learning. The instability of Internet and software problems may cause difficulties especially in synchronous teaching.

2 COURSE CONTENT, LEARNING OUTCOMES AND ASSIGNMENTS

2.1 General description

Two universities were jointly organizing two course implementations on circular economy in infra construction, *Course 1* carried out in academic year 2017-2018 and *Course 2* in 2018-2019. The *Course 1* was designed and realized together with industrial and institutional partners, such as Ministry of the Environment, Finnish Transport Agency and consulting office Ramboll Finland Ltd.

Both courses were aimed to the university degree students and to the professionals. The courses were designed to 5 credits ECTS, which means 133 h of studying. All the

lectures were given in Finnish. In *Course 1* the participants from companies paid a small fee. In *Course 2*, there was no fee thanks to a small financial support received from the Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra. To promote the information on potential of by-products, the municipal and environmental regulators were invited to follow the lectures online for free in *Course 1*.

The core of the courses consists of six intensive days organized once per month. The lectures were sent online by AC and recorded. In *Course 1*, the content and lecturers were designed together with the industry producing potential by-products. As for the *Course 2*, the content was planned mainly by the university based on the experience from *Course 1*. The topics of the both course implementations included e.g., material requirements for typical applications, properties of various secondary materials, such as demolition wastes and ashes and slags from energy and steel industry, legislation, environmental risks and permission processes and design criteria.

In *Course 1*, lectures were given either in Tampere or in Pasila outside the university campus, and participants and lecturers were travelling to the lecturing location. In *Course 2*, the lectures were given either in Tampere or Espoo, or from any location the lecturer chose, and distributed online to participants sitting in a lecturing room either in Tampere or Otaniemi, at their working places or at home.

The learning outcomes of the course on *Circular Economy in Infrastructures* were derived from the experiences of Finnish UUMA2 demonstration projects and discussions with experts. The aim was to provide a wide knowledge on recycled materials and their influence on the design and performance of the infrastructures.

2.2 Participants

The interest for the courses was high. The total amount of participants of *Course 1* was 162, of which 40% were authorities, i.e. municipal or provincial regulators or officials, participating through an on-line connection. In contact learning the actual number of students was 98, of which 80 completed the course (81.6%). At the beginning of the academic year the total amount of participants in *Course 2* was 68. The actual number of participants completing the course was 47 (69.1%).

Fig. 2. Background of participants on two courses on circular economy, *Course 1* 2017-2018 on left and *Course 2* 2018-2019 on right.

The division of the participants on these two courses into three main groups, 1) university degree students, 2) authorities, and 3) designers and consultants, is presented in *Fig. 2*.

2.3 Learning assignments

A learning platform Moodle was used for communication and to distribute the information and links to AC recordings. At the beginning of each contact day a multiple-choice test based on lectures of previous day was organized in Moodle to assess and motivate the learning. There was no final exam.

In order to get the credits, the participation to contact learning was compulsory during the *Course 1*. In *Course 2*, the on-line participation controlled by a password, was also accepted as participation. If the participant was missing the lectures, it was possible to compensate it by doing substitute tasks, e.g. writing a learning diary based on lecture slides and the lecture recordings. Diaries were returned to Moodle.

The participants were divided into groups. The groups were pre-formed in order to mix the degree students from different universities and adult students to promote the information sharing and cooperative learning. In the *Course 1* the groups were quite big (max 12 participants) due the large number of participants. In the *Course 2* the groups were a bit smaller (max 8 participants).

One of the main differences between the two implementations was the activation of the students. In *Course 2* the students prepared in groups a compact material card and a 30-minute presentation about a given secondary material. The presentation was performed to all, either online through AC or as a pre-recorded video, and an expert from industry were commenting the student presentations.

The core part of the course was a project work, where the groups searched and gathered information about given secondary materials, selected a suitable material and designed the structure for a factual application. The applications used in both courses were real cases from public infra construction projects of which enough public information was available for design. The results of the design work were presented to other students as a poster. The other students evaluated the posters in an electrical form. In the *Course 1* the posters were printed and presented in a poster walk. In the *Course 2* the posters were presented as pdf-files in Moodle.

3 RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Evaluation of learning activity

Learning analytics from Moodle was used to evaluate of the activity of the students. Unfortunately, the detailed analytics from the *Course 1* were no longer available at the time of this study. The data from the *Course 2* was analyzed with quite simple methods using Microsoft Excel.

The reports of AC provide data on number of participants on each “meeting”, as they are called in AC, and detailed information when each participant has created and ended a connection. This data was used to assess the online participation activity.

3.2 Feedback questionnaires and interviews

The feedback was collected in the *Course 1* after every contact day by a Webropol questionnaire. The focus of the questionnaire was on the content of each day and the practical management of the course. In *Course 2*, a common Webropol questionnaire was sent to everybody after the course. In addition, separate feedback surveys were made to the university students at the end of the course. Besides, during the *Course 1*, three students were interviewed by a professional magazine.

In addition, fifteen participants representing both courses and various backgrounds were chosen for a personal interview by email. The questions involved the affect of participants with different background on one’s learning.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Activity in Adobe Connect

The number of online connections and number of actual online participants during lecturing days in *Course 1* and *Course 2* are shown in *Fig. 4*. The opening day on *Course 2* was divided into two parts, hence the morning program was together with parallel course on circular economy in house construction.

Fig. 4. Number of online connections in AC during the lecturing days on *Course 1* (left) and *Course 2* (right).

During one lecturing day, a participant could have started several online connections, especially if any technical problems have occurred. In some cases, there were several persons using the same connection, especially during *Course 1*, where the municipal and provincial officials were invited to follow the lectures online for free.

On *Course 1* there were significantly larger number of connections due to unexperienced users and technical problems in internet connection. Also, the number of online participants were a bit higher than on *Course 2*. In average, there were 36 online participants on *Course 1*. One connection from a municipality or a Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment typically corresponded two to four online listeners. The most popular day among the authorities was the third day concentrating on the renewing environmental legislation.

On *Course 2* the lectures were presented alternately from two or three places and lecturers of both universities were online, increasing the connections of lecturers. The number of online participants varied between 24...34 on *Course 2*.

4.2 Activity in Moodle

The detailed data from the activity of *Course 1* were not available. The general activity based on monthly Moodle records presented in *Fig. 4* shows that the activities were typically the highest in the beginning of the course and an increase in activity is noticed shortly before and during the contact days.

Fig. 4. The monthly summary of the activities during the *Course 1* on left and on *Course 2* on right based on Moodle records.

The activity in the *Course 2* decreases during the course more than in the *Course 1*. In fact, the lowering of the activity in the *Course 1* was only 20% as in the *Course 2* the decrease was 60%. The total amount of logs in the *Course 1* was naturally higher because of the higher number of students. Based on the logs, the most visited point

in Moodle were the assessments: the results of exams and the grading of the group work.

The Interactions in Moodle can be divided in six different groups according to Gómez-Aguilar et al (2015): *learner-learner*; *content-content*, *learner-content*, *teacher-teacher*; *learner-teacher*; *teacher-content* [7]. In both courses the main interactions may be classified to learner-content interactions. Learner-learner interactions, such as discussions were not so popular, when a post to discussion forum or starting a discussion were considered. The groups used other media, e.g. WhatsApp or Microsoft applications to interact. Therefore, the Moodle logs are not representing the teamwork activity and the commitment of the group.

4.3 Learning results vs activity

Drop out percentage in the *Course 1* was 18% and in *Course 2* 30%, in the average. In the latter course, 50% of the authorities starting the course dropped out; in other words, they didn't take the Moodle quizzes or participate to the group work. However, they could be following the lectures online. Based on these results, the formal learning requiring student activity is not as attractive for working learners as passive listening, especially if there is no external motivation such as participation fee. On the other hand, most of the degree students passed all the learning assignments, even though the course was not compulsory. In addition, the high drop-out rate on *Course 2* added the work load of the remaining students.

When the activity of a single student in *Course 2* is compared to the grades or success in the course, a clear difference is discovered: the activity of the student with low points (total amount of activities 360 in Moodle) is only 50% from the activity of the best student (total amount of activities 711). The student with lowest grades visited Moodle only during contact days. Also, the group which got the highest grades from the group work, had higher number of activities (total 2225) than the group with lowest points (total 2026). However, there is no clear correlation between the logs and grades, since the purpose, outcome and type of the activity are affecting on the learning results; just the number of clicks is not telling about the quality of the activity.

When the adult learners and degree students are compared, the difference in Moodle activity is evident. The degree students are experienced and effective Moodle users needing less clicks to find their way, resulting lower number of logs, while the adult learners are less experienced and clicking more often (see *Fig. 5*).

Fig. 5. The summary of the Moodle logs of the degree students on the left and the participants from companies on the right based on Moodle records during *Course 2*.

4.4 Feedback analysis

The feedback of the *Course 1* has been described briefly in reference [8]. In general, the feedback of both courses was very positive. Based on the questionnaires, the participants were especially content with the topicality of the course content and the lectures given by experts with practical experience. Most of the respondents considered the learning assignments beneficial for their learning. For example, in *Course 2* over 60% of 21 respondents considered that the material card, presentation and design project supported their learning and gave additional value. All respondents would recommend the course.

In general, the online connection was good. There were some minor problems with voice (mentioned by 6 of 11 answers). The major difficulty was the group work: there were problems with the division of the labor, partly due to the lack of face-to-face contact in *Course 2*, resulting uneven workload. However, the co-operation between degree students and working learners was considered beneficial (*Fig. 6*).

Fig. 6. Some results from the feedback questionnaire on *Course 2*.

5 DISCUSSION

The information the Moodle analytics is providing on student activity seems promising. However, it doesn't tell the whole truth since the learners were using other communication and co-operation platforms, such as Google Docs and WhatsApp. The main interactions were learner-content interactions.

Co-operation learning is beneficial for motivated learners. However, the achieving of active co-operation in online course requires much more effort than in contact teaching with possibilities to face-to-face contact during e.g. lecturing breaks. Especially older students are used to passive listening of lectures instead of active involvement and learning by doing.

In addition, the inadequate e-learning skills limited the student activity, especially among the further education learners. This should have been considered in course planning by organizing either extra activities or compulsory face-to-face group meetings.

The learning results depend strongly on the motivation, both internal and external, of the learner. The drop-up rate was much lower among degree students, even though the course is not compulsory. A fee is also a motivating factor to attend the lectures, but not strong enough to urge to work between the contact days. Especially voluntary, working further education learners are unprepared and unwilling to participate in group work and other learning tasks requiring activity outside the lectures, mainly due to the lack of time. Free education without credits results high no-show and drop-out rate.

These two courses on Circular Economy involved over 300 people, including the lecturers. This is a significant figure considering the size of the Finnish infra construction sector, both demonstrating the need for education and launching a necessary disruptive change towards CE.

The increasing need for lifelong learning is recognized by the Finnish universities and decision makers. The collected experience will be used in development of future courses, where the degree students and further education learners are combined, to achieve cooperative and continuous learning.

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